

**THE EVOLUTION OF URBAN HOUSING ARCHITECTURE IN INDIA: A HISTORICAL
AND SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS**

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Abstract

Housing has many social, economic and political dimensions. Both at the settlement level as well as within the dwelling unit, space is organized in conformity with the social considerations. There had always been a distinct imprint on the nature of settlement structure in the past. Old megalithic and iron age archeological sites existed in India. The earliest settlements Indus Valley civilization in India recognized for its comprehensive urban planning. Houses built out of stone and mud bricks with uniform and identical in their characteristics. With the end of Indus Valley civilization and the rise of different empires and dynasties throughout the country began reflecting the use of rock-cut architecture and stone construction exhibited the values and traditions of the community. Further the country witnessed a rise in dominance by the emperial rulers and during British and European rule through typical architectural features and native architectural style. After independence developing of planned cities emerged. By the 1990s with the onset of liberalization and the entry of the private sector into real estate. The stories of the apartment buildings grew, the cost of living increased and the houses in rural areas have also started adopting the materials used in the urban context, concrete, and glass. In the present time excess demand for affordable dwellings. Small rental market and an oversupply of high-end housing seen especially in urban areas.

KEYWORDS: - Civilization, Settlement, Community, Urban planning, Urban Society, affordable dwellings, Social change, Changing in Housing Pattern

Introduction

Housing is key for well-being and for spatial and social mobility. Our ancestral lives in informal housing and caves. Every part of India has distinctive character of architecture in housing. The rural and urban both types of areas have distinctive characteristics. The architecture of Wadas of Peshwas of Maharashtra and Mandya Pradesh, Mohallas of community of Madhya Pradesh and Utarpradesh, Havelis heritage of Rajasthan and Gujarat, Kothis of all north Indian states, Pols of Ahmedabad Gujarat, Chetiar houses of Chettinad or in Portuguese and Brahmin colonies of Goa are similar cases where housing has functioned as sense of togetherness. The housing in these areas follows some architectural expression and the built environment is settled in the surrounding landscape and nearby buildings. The human scale has been given importance and hence they are comfortable to eyes of people of all age groups. The use of local materials and technologies are the primary means of sustainability. Modernization of such use to suit today's climatic conditions and changing lifestyle is the area where profession of architecture may help. The gated communities of the present day have brought a culture where the privacy has been given important priority. In order to maintain privacy, sometimes human

interaction is just ignored and it raises sense of loneliness and mental diseases governed by it. There are commonality between the past, present and future housing are human beings, comfort conditions, and community. The design considerations for human nature and feelings can be learned from past and incorporated in the present.

Aims and Objective

This article throws light on the differences that present day housing and the traditional housing types in general. The studied typologies have been called as traditional housing form and present-day housing refers to high density, medium rise apartment housing coming in fringe areas of growing Indian cities. The common part between the past, present and future housing are human beings, comfort conditions, and community. The design considerations for human nature and feelings can be learned from past and incorporated in the present.

Methodology

Primary data collected from architecture books to study an architectural splendor in Indian housing from past to present and secondary data collected from research paper and article and from internet. Combining primary data from architecture books with secondary data from research papers and articles allows for a multi-faceted understanding of how Indian housing has evolved. Use diagrams and photographs from primary sources to illustrate points made in secondary analyses. With insights gained from both data types, you can critically assess how traditional architectural practices have been adapted to modern needs and challenges.

Aspects of housing from old traditional housing to present day modern housing

In this article author try to explain aspects in housing through chronological order with settlement examples evolved from past to present. The earliest settlements in India dates back to around 3000 B.C.E. during the Indus Valley civilization, recognized for its comprehensive urban planning. Built using stone and mud bricks, and timber, all the houses were uniform and identical in their characteristics and located around the citadel in the center of the city. The houses were one to three-storeyed with courtyards in the center, connected to a common drainage system. The Indus valley civilization had a rich and systematic social life, with strong family organizations and a predominantly matriarchal society. Social amusements included hunting wild animals, bullfighting, fishing, and clay modeling. The children of artisans learned skills in crafting from their parents. The Indus valley civilization subsisted primarily by farming, supplemented by commerce. Wheat and six-row barley were grown, and domesticated animals included dogs and cats, humped and shorthorn cattle, domestic fowl, and possibly pigs, camels, and buffalo. Harappan people created sculpture, seals, pottery, and jewelry from materials, such as terracotta, metal, and stone, developed the first accurate system of standardized weights and measures, some as accurate as to 1.6 mm.

With the decline of the Indus Valley civilization and the rise of different empires and dynasties throughout the country, the evolution of housing in India began reflecting the use of rock-cut architecture and stone construction by 1000 BCE. The carved walls of viharas exhibited the values and traditions of the community.

Figure-1

Layout Plan of Dholavira Archeological Site at Gujarat

Figure-2

Common Drainage System

The viharas accommodated houses, gathering spaces, verandas, monasteries, and several community spaces, and had an optimal spatial dispositioning. Rock cut architecture were originally dormitories but were later converted into residence-cum-temple caves. It is a type of ancient Indian art that is often related to various religions and religious activities. The stories represented on the cave walls or through sculptures are valuable sources of historical information. The architecture also reflects the changing realities. Rock-cut architecture is a significant part of India's history and cultural heritage. It provides valuable insights into the social and economic life of ancient India, and helps us understand the evolution of Indian society through a socio-political perspective. The architecture also showcases the engineering skills of the time, with ancient Indian artisans creating elaborate structures with precision.

Figure -3 & 4
Buddhist viharas

Rock cut architecture

These are the residential places for the Buddhist priests. They consists of a main hall entered by a door way. They also contain assembly hall, dining chambers, from the halls deep into the rocks, cells are provided for meditation. Best examples of rock cut architecture.

Further during the 1000 A.D., the country witnessed a rise in dominance by the Mughals, Rajputs, Marathas, and the Sikhs. Though the typical architectural styles of these empires were evident in the public structures, such as the Indo-Islamic style of Mughals, Indo-Aryan style of Rajputs, Wadas of Marathas, the style limited itself to the wealthy section of the society, the urban areas, and the rulers.

Wadas, a type of large mansion in western India, are a significant part of Maharashtra's cultural and architectural heritage. They reflect the Marathas' pride, religion, traditions, and history, and were once the homes of the Peshwas and other members of the administrative system. Wada symbolizes the tales of Pune's rich culture and heritage. They are historical symbol of Pune. They are famous for their typical architectural language and the traditional architecture of old city of the Pune.

Wadas – Exploring the Traditional Houses of Maharashtra. Wadas are traditional houses that evolved during the Maratha period. They are a characteristic building form that vary in size and form. Wada's were used for both domestic as well as political purposes. These are basically two to three storied oldest structures in the city generally square or rectangular in shape with courtyard at the center. Wadas basically a big structure with the courtyard having introvert design.

Figure- 5 & 6 Wadas houses at Maharashtra

This type of planning was introduced by Marathas to safe guard their families from outsiders. The design is amalgamation of Mughal, Rajasthani, and Gujarati architecture combined with the local construction techniques.

Pole houses at Ahmedabad

Pole architecture is an interesting evolution in urban living space. Pols are self-contained settlements with narrow streets, beautiful houses, and separate entrances. The physical boundaries of a pol are often based on the interrelationships among its inhabitants. Pols are traditional housing structures in Ahmedabad, India that date back to 1738, during the Mughal-Maratha rule. They were originally built as a safety precaution during communal disturbances, and each pol was once a self-contained settlement for families of the same caste, religion, or occupation. The pol is usually run by a panch, which consists of community elders who take care of the day-to-day activities of the neighborhood. Pols are generally made up of people belonging to the same community, and one can often find a temple or a mosque dedicated to the community's belief. Due to the small streets, homes can see and interact with other residents. The interconnected system of winding streets fosters a tight-knit community. As a consequence of the requirement for social gathering and protection, urban compact fabric with shared walls generates shaded areas standing upright as a human habitat that is responsive to the climate. It has

a brilliantly defined urban sense, unlike the gated plots of the modern suburbs, and is almost like an infinite fabric where the mass proportions and clustering are almost the same as the open areas.

Figure-7, Floor Plan of A Pol House

Figure -8 Layout of Pol Ahmedabad

Following the Mughals, several European powers such as British, Dutch, Portuguese and the French invaded India and introduced their native style of architecture to the regions they ruled. British colonial architecture is a style that incorporates English architecture with local elements to suit the context. British colonial architecture is grand and stately, with high ceilings, floor-to-ceiling windows, and tall marble pillars and arches. Dutch colonial architecture is a style of domestic architecture characterized by gambrel roofs with curved eaves along the length of the house. An example of Dutch architecture in India is the Mattancherry Palace, also known as the Dutch Palace, in Kochi, Kerala, which was built in the mid-16th century.

However, a major shift in the evolution of housing in India and settlements in the country was marked in British rule due to the rise in trade and a new cultural setting. The newly emerging residential buildings come up weren't independently built, instead, were built in colonies owing to a particular community or workplace. These colonies were basically built for British people. For the lower-income groups started living in 'Chawls' a housing typology known for having '*kholis*' or rooms for the tenants connected by a single passage on one side of the structure and having shared sanitation facilities per floor.

Figure -9 Victoria Memorial, Kolkatta

Figure-10, Old House Colonial Style

Chawls in Mumbai are typically built around a central courtyard, with rooms grouped around a corridor. The corridor usually faces a street and has the main entrances of the houses. The corridor has two strands of rooms, one in front and one at the rear. Chawls are a type of middle-class housing in Mumbai, India. They were built in the 19th and 20th centuries by landlords to accommodate migrants

from villages. Chawls can be single- or multi-storied, with a ground floor and two or three floors above.

Figure – 11 & 12, Chawl at Mumbai

One end of the corridor has a staircase, while the other end typically has a set of toilets that are shared by the households. Chawls are large tenement houses, often multi-story buildings, that are common in Mumbai, India. They are characterized by their cramped living spaces and dense population. Chawls are typically built around a central courtyard, with rooms grouped around a corridor and divided into single or double room units. Bathrooms are usually shared between the residents of each floor. Many chawls were built in the 19th and 20th centuries by private landlords or the government to accommodate migrants from villages due to the rising employment opportunities in early Mumbai. Residents of chawls sometimes cite a sense of community where everything is shared amongst themselves. The cramped design of chawls forces social interaction between residents and very often special occasions such as weddings or religious festivals are celebrated communally.

After independence, The government of India thus came up with several Housing schemes to deal with the issue such as LIG Housing Scheme, MIG Housing Scheme, Slum Clearance and Improvement Scheme, etc. and also emphasized developing planned cities. By the 1990s liberalization by former primeminister Dr. Manmohansingh and the entry of the private sector into real estate, there was a mass development into the urban areas of the country. Since then, the size of the houses shrunk, the stories of the apartment buildings grew, the cost of living increased, and also led to the growth of several illegal settlements, ‘slums’ in the urban areas. On the contrary, in rural areas people also started adopting the materials used in house construction and in the urban context, concrete, and glass used.

In the present time, Indiaongoing urbanization, and particularly rural urban migration, will intensify demand for affordable housing, The 2016 Real Estate (Regulation and Development) Act, which seeks to enhance transparency, protect the interests of homebuyers and boost investment in the real estate sector, helped improve the market situation. By improving the collateral security, the law can also facilitate access to housing finance. The Housing for All program that aims to provide a home for every Indian by 2022 is a good way forward in reducing the shortage.

Modernization and Housing in India

Charles Correa attempted to implement traditional techniques of sheltering roofs, sunken courts, outdoor rooms etc. into the organizational housing typologies developed by Frank Lloyd Wright and Le Corbusier in his luxury apartments in the Kanchenjunga block. This leads many committed designers to realize that their function could be to bring expertise to an uncontrollable informal sector

at the level of technical assistance.

Figure- 13 & 14, Government Housing

Figure-15, Chandigarh Sector Plan

Figure-16, Gandhinagar- Planned City

In Delhi, numerous Housing colonies were designed as close-knit aggregations, such as Raj Rewal's Sheik Sarai Housing (1976) and The Asian Games Village (1982) as an attempt to combine modern housing principles with traditional techniques of architecture indigenous to the area of construction.

Modern Housing Layout

We can see today in city like Ahmedabad. The premium housing apartment and low rise scheme like 3,4,5,6,7 BHK with levis amenities within and some good examples of housing layout design by Indian known architect Charles correa, B.V. doshi and many more . India has many types of housing, including apartments, bungalows, villas, condos, townhouses, and duplex houses.

Figure- 17, Belapur Incremental Housing Project, Community Space Within Township

**Figure-18. Kanchanjunga Apartment,
Mumbai**

**Figure-19, Aranya Low-Cost Housing,
Indore**

Sociological Implications of Changing Housing Patterns

The sociological implications of changing housing patterns in India are profound, reflecting broader shifts in social structure, family dynamics, and community cohesion. The transition from traditional joint-family homes to nuclear housing, especially in urban areas, has facilitated greater individual autonomy, particularly for women. This shift allows family members to pursue personal goals and careers, fostering independence and empowerment.

Positive Impacts on Family and Social Life

The shift from joint family homes to nuclear-centric apartments has promoted privacy and autonomy. Smaller, independent units give family members—especially women—greater freedom to pursue individual goals, such as careers and education, which may be challenging in a traditional joint-family setup. This privacy fosters closer relationships within nuclear families, as members can focus on their immediate kin without extended obligations. In gated communities, shared amenities and organized events provide a sense of belonging, encouraging residents to form social bonds despite being geographically separated from extended families.

Negative Impacts on Family and Social Life

However, these evolving housing patterns also bring challenges. The decline of extended-family homes has led to weaker intergenerational bonds, as nuclear families become isolated from the wisdom, guidance, and support that elder family members traditionally provide. This isolation can lead to reduced familial cohesion, loneliness, and even elder neglect, as young families increasingly opt for independent living arrangements. High-rise apartments, while efficient, often restrict spontaneous social interactions, contributing to a sense of anonymity and reducing communal bonds. Gated communities, designed to offer safety and exclusivity, can inadvertently create socio-economic and cultural barriers, limiting interactions across different social classes and contributing to social stratification.

3. Sociological Perspectives on Housing Evolution

The **functionalist perspective** views traditional housing structures as promoting social stability and interdependence, as they allowed family members to support each other economically, socially, and emotionally. The move to individual housing units can destabilize these functions, yet it fosters adaptation to modern urban demands.

The **conflict perspective** highlights how urban housing patterns mirror economic inequalities. While gated communities and modern apartments cater to affluent families, low-income groups often reside in informal settlements or poorly maintained public housing, reinforcing social and economic divides in urban spaces.

Finally, **symbolic interactionism** emphasizes how changing housing designs reflect shifts in social identity and aspirations. High-rise apartments and gated communities represent status and aspirations of upward mobility, signalling a departure from traditional communal lifestyles to more privatized and modern identities.

Conclusion

The common and identifying character of housing can be seen in India. Indian architecture is all about Resilience, Caring and Sharing, Pluralism of existence, vitality and response to climate. Every part of India has such character of architecture in housing. The rural and urban both types of areas have such characteristics. The differences that present day housing and the traditional houses in general, the design considerations for human nature and feelings can be learned from past and incorporated in the present. The Housing for All program that aims to provide a home for every Indian by 2022 is a good way forward in reducing the shortage.

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